

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT SYSTEMS IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT. In today's market economy, numerous well-developed countries have already commenced utilizing international assessment methods. The evaluation system helps the countries to enhance the quality of education more better and create an innovative learning environment, increase student literacy.

Keywords: The importance of assessment, learner's expertise, knowledge, skills, quality of education, PISA, PIRLIS, TIMSS, TALIS, creative, assessment, qualifications.

Аннотация. В сегодняшней рыночной экономике многие хорошо развитые страны уже начали использовать международные методы оценки. Система оценки помогает странам еще лучше повысить качество образования и создать инновационную среду обучения, повысить грамотность учащихся.

Ключевые слова: Важность оценивания, опыт учащегося, знания, навыки, качество образования, PISA, PIRLIS, TIMSS, TALIS, креативность, оценка, квалификация.

It is scientifically proved that assessment is regarded as one of the vital system in education as well as teaching. It plays an essential role in identifying not only a learner's comprehension and how the learner gains the expertise but also the shortcoming of knowledge. Moreover, assessing helps to provide information about what each of the students knows, what they understand and what they are capable of, but their results are important for all participants of the process, including students, parents, teachers, and used to improve curricula and teaching methods.

Assessment is another way of measuring expertise of students. Komil Jolilov says that "Assessment is the process of measuring the level of formation of any domain (a set of knowledge, skills, skills and competencies) in learners (test takers)" [1;10]. In agreement with these points, we consider assessment as a process of measuring the level of achievement of educational goals at a certain stage of the educational process, determining and analyzing the results based on predetermined criteria, and this process provides us with information on the acquired knowledge. enables the systematic collection, analysis and use of data.

In order to enhance and innovate assessing systems and broaden the usage of variety assessment methods in education, international assessment systems have been utilized in our country. These international assessment programs will greatly help to update the content of the education system, create an innovative learning environment, improve the quality of education and increase student literacy. As a result of the reforms implemented in our country in recent years, it is huge that economic growth indicators are achieved, qualified personnel in all fields and increasing the demand for qualified specialists. It's self-evident to increase the interest of our students in lessons and teachers' every requires increased attention to comprehensive education. Above that the requirements are very important for the education system in most foreign countries education by evaluating and monitoring the development of such fields of education and science means that it is necessary to attract

advanced practices aimed at improving the quality to the field. Involving such advanced experiences in our educational system is the knowledge potential of students helps to increase and creative thinking.

We will look through some types of international assessment in the following:

PISA - international program of assessment of educational achievements of students;

PIRLS - a defining international study of level of reading and comprehension of the text;

TIMSS – international quality research monitoring Mathematics and Science at School;

TALISS- international study of teaching and learning.

PISA - is an international evaluation program, the main goal of which is 15-year-olds students' reading literacy, mathematics, natural sciences consists in evaluating literacy levels in the form of various tests. PISA is the OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment. PISA measures 15-year-olds' ability to use their reading, mathematics and science knowledge and skills to meet real-life challenges. This projects to students' creative and critical thinking, acquired knowledge assessing life skills and then applying these skills is to encourage creation. This program was introduced in 1997, every three years will be conducted once. The impact of the PISA program on public policy in the field of education showing that each country has its own education based on the results of the research identifying the achievements and shortcomings in the field, compared to other countries compares its position. The assessing program has attracted a number of countries. Since 2000, PISA has involved more than 100 countries and economies and around 3 700 000 students worldwide. PISA 2022 focused on mathematics, with an additional test of creative thinking.

Initial results of PISA 2022 were released on 5 December 2023. 81 countries and economies took part in PISA 2022. PISA 2025 will focus on science and include a new assessment of foreign languages. It will also include the innovative domain of Learning in the Digital World which aims to measure students' ability to engage in self-regulated learning while using digital tools[3].

PIRLS- (Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study) is a primary.

international assessment of the level of reading comprehension of the students of the class. More than 50 countries are participating in the PIRLS study. The target of this international research owns different educational system. For instance, defining the reading comprehension skills among primary school children and various achievements of students. This program was organized in 2001 by the association of international educational achievement assessment [2;3].

TIMSS- the main goal of the TIMSS international research is the comparative assessment of the quality of education in mathematics and natural sciences in primary and secondary schools. motivation is also evaluated. The study is designed so that its results track trends in math and science education in participating countries every 4 years as 4th graders move to 8th grade. Thus, the educational achievement of elementary and middle school students, as well as changes in mathematics and science education during the transition from elementary school to high school, are monitored.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to the decision of the General Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Preparation for PIRLS, TIMSS, PISA and TALIS international studies of organizations. Viewing and ensuring participation in them are defined. It is worth mentioning that these international evaluation programs require the content renewal of the educational system of our Republic, the creation of an innovative educational environment, and an increase in the quality of education.

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